

Deliverable D5.2

Biolmage Archive infrastructure and deposition pipeline for versioned reference annotations

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Change Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of changes
v0.1	16.02.24	Matthew Hartley	Initial draft
v0.2	26.02.24	Dorothea Dörr, Arrate Muñoz Barrutia, Aybüke Yoldas	Final draft approved for submission

Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
D	Deliverable
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
JSON	Javascript Serialised Object Notation
LinkML	Link Markup Language
MIFA	Metadata, Incentives, Formats, Accessibility
ML	Machine Learning
OME	Open Microscopy Environment
PU	Public
RI	Research Infrastructure
v	Version
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

Table of contents

Acronyms and Abbreviations	2
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Description of work	5
2.1 Underlying data and metadata model	5
2.2 Offline form submission	6
2.3 Web based submission	6
2.4 Data presentation, search and access	9
Presentation	9
Search	9
Access	9
3. Conclusion	10

Executive Summary

AI4Life aims to democratise access to modern Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods in biological imaging by bridging the gap between life science and computer vision researchers to broaden the reach of cutting-edge techniques. A key part of widening access to AI approaches is improving accessibility of the rich variety of annotated imaging data that is necessary to train, evaluate, and benchmark AI models. The work described in this deliverable creates a deposition pipeline for archiving and sharing image annotations. It builds on the metadata standards (MIFA) established earlier in the project (**D5.1**).

Image annotations such as segmentations, bounding boxes or point landmarks, are the critical components that render image datasets suitable for supervised AI model training, as well as providing important biological context to raw pixel / voxel data. This deposition pipeline will both encourage the reuse of annotated images for model training as well as support the reproducibility of biological results that depend on image annotations.

1. Introduction

While image annotations are a crucial part of rendering image datasets “AI ready”, in the biological sciences, the datasets that couple images and annotations are scarce and they are published in scattered repositories without common standards.

One of the aims of the AI4Life project is to widen access to, and improve the FAIRness (FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) of, these annotated image datasets. In the early phases of the project, we began this process by developing the metadata standards needed to support long term open sharing of annotated images (**D5.1**). Here we describe the key next step of implementing a deposition system which allows long term archival of image annotations according to those standards.

2. Description of work

Support for the deposition, search, presentation and retrieval of image annotations relies on the underlying data and metadata models developed in D5.1. Drawing from these models, we implement two complementary routes for deposition of image annotations – fully web-based submission (most suitable for novice users), and offline form submission (suitable for those with command line tool experience, and as part of a programmatic deposition pipeline).

2.1 Underlying data and metadata model

The MIFA metadata schema, developed earlier within the project, is programmatically described using the LinkML markup language. From this canonical schema description, we use the LinkML software suite to create data classes for the Python programming language. These are then used to generate the underlying components for the two forms of deposition we support – offline forms and an online web submission tool (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 – workflow for supporting annotation deposition

2.2 Offline form submission

Using the schema, we generate YAML template forms (see Figure 2). These can be completed/edited using any standard text editing tool and provide a mechanism by which data stewards can collaborate on data submission.

```
annotations:
  "Segmentation masks":
    annotation_overview: |-
      Segmentations masks of human cell nuclei curated by experts from a model prediction
    annotation_method: |-
      Nuclei image annotation was performed by students and expert biologists trained by a disease expert
    annotation_confidence_level: |-
      Curators had between 10 and 15 years of experience in cancer pathology
    annotation_criteria: |-
      "The annotation of nuclei in tissue sections or tumor touch imprints is challenging and may not be
    annotation_coverage: |-
      All the images in the dataset were annotated
version:
  "Segmentation masks":
    version: "v1.1"
    timestamp: 2015-03-22 01:49:21
    changes: |-
      The new version of the dataset includes 20 additional annotations (files seg34.tif to seg54.tif)
    previous_version: "v1.0"
```

Figure 2 – section of YAML form for annotation deposition

Importantly, these forms can also be generated programmatically which supports interoperability between software tools or institutional data management systems, and public archives.

2.3 Web based submission

While text forms are useful for data stewards, and others with specific expertise in data management, the majority of users are non-experts who are best supported by a web-based system. To this end, we have implemented online form-based submission.

This operates through the [BioStudies](#) database's Angular (Javascript) based submission tool system, which supports different interactive web forms via a templating system. We generate templates for this system using the MIFA metadata schema as described above.

After beginning a submission, users are presented with a dialog to select the type of submission they are making (see Figure 3). This allows them to choose between depositing images or images and annotations, or depositing only annotations. Once this is selected, a full interactive submission form is presented (see Figure 4).

New submission

Please select a BioStudies collection that you are submitting to.

Imaging datasets must be submitted using the "BioImages" template. Submissions that do not do so may have their release delayed. For further details please see the [EMBL-EBI policy on imaging data submissions](#).

	BioImages BioImage Archive Study
	Default General submission
	MicrobioRaman Microbiological Raman Spectroscopy Data
	BioImages BioImage Archive Annotations Submission (for Image Annotations only)

Figure 3 – selection of image annotation deposition

Each field in this form provides a brief supporting explanation of its purpose, together with one or more examples (see Figure 5).

Figure 4 – online form for completing annotation metadata fields

Figure 5 – example field description

The submitters can link to the source images for each annotation using the file list (a component of the submission that allows for the specification of individual file-level metadata) or using the link field of the submission form at the dataset level.

Once the submission is complete, a unique identifier is assigned for that submission, and submitters can choose the release date for their annotations. This determines when data will be made publicly available, and can be changed, for example, to align with manuscript submission.

Data submitters also receive a sharing link, which can be used to provide private access to the submission before release, typically used to provide anonymous access to reviewers of an accompanying manuscript.

2.4 Data presentation, search and access

Presentation

Once public, each submission is accessible via a unique permanent URI. This URI displays a landing page which shows the submission metadata, as well as providing access to the individual annotation data files, see example in Figure 6.

Segmentation masks for human cells expressing a sphingolipid marker from the study S-BIAD144

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Accession S-BIAD916

Description This dataset contains segmentation masks generated with Cellpose for a subset of the images included in the BioImage Archive submission S-BIAD144

Keyword segmentation, AI, Cellpose, sphingolipid

Acknowledgements We thank the submitters of S-BIAD144 for publicly sharing the images segmented in this dataset

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Segmentation masks 20 files [Show](#) [Download](#)

Annotation overview Segmentation masks of individual human cells in culture, curated from a model prediction

Annotation method Images were segmented using the Cytoplasm 2.0 ('cyto2') model in Cellpose. Only channel 0 of the multidimensional images, showing sphingolipid (pacSph) localisation, was used for segmentation. The segmentations were subsequently curated by a scientist and any segmentation errors were eliminated.

Annotation confidence level The scientist curating the annotations has 9 years of experience in cell biology

Annotation coverage Only 10 out of 223 images have been annotated. All cells per image have been segmented

File List [file_list_annotations_sb1ad144_v2.json](#) [JSON](#) [XML](#) [PageTab](#)

Data files

Show 5 entries Search:

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Siz
<input type="checkbox"/>	experimentA_06_WT_mock_cp_mask.tif	8 K
<input type="checkbox"/>	experimentA_15_SGPL1_PDMP_cp_mask.tif	4 K
<input type="checkbox"/>	experimentA_12_SGPL1_PDMP_cp_mask.tif	5 K
<input type="checkbox"/>	experimentA_10_WT_Miglustat_cp_mask.tif	11
<input type="checkbox"/>	experimentA_02_WT_PDMP_cp_mask.tif	5 K

Showing 1 to 5 of 20 entries

Previous 1 2 3 4 Next

[Download all files](#)

Linked Information

Figure 6 – example landing page for an annotation submission, highlighting the MIFA (annotation-specific) metadata

Search

All of the metadata fields accompanying the annotations are indexed and therefore searchable using the Archive's search system, which is based on the Apache Solr search platform (itself based on the underlying Apache Lucene library).

Access

Individual files can be downloaded by multiple routes/protocols:

- Directly through the web interface using HTTPS
- By FTP (File Transfer Protocol)
- By the accelerated Aspera protocol

- Using the Globus transfer system

Together, these protocols provide a balance of simplicity versus performance for data access. Both files and accompanying metadata can also be accessed via the BioStudies API. This supports global search and access to individual records, providing responses in JSON format.

3. Conclusion

Image annotations are critical for training, benchmarking and validating new AI models, as well as understanding the provenance chain of existing published models. Long term preservation of these annotations, together with their corresponding images, provides important future scientific value. The enhancements to the BiImage Archive allow it to act as a sustainable long term home for these image annotations, together with the key metadata that maximises their reuse potential.

Further work will focus on extending programmatic access to support integration of these annotations with models in the BiImage Model Zoo, to enable automated application of models to BiImage Archive image/annotation data. This will support both model benchmarking, and cross-model comparison for individual datasets.

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